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INTELLIGENT MERGING OF XML DOCUMENTS FOR DISTRIBUTED COLLABORATION

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Abstract

XML as a meta-language has emerged as the lingua franca of the internet. It is applied to define the formats of databases, and documents. It is also used as exchange format for a large number of applications. This wide applicability is both a blessing and a curse: Most related tools are tailored to a particular use-case, which means that they can deal only with special dialects. In this paper, we will focus on a document-centric view on XML.

Several papers have been published on finding changes in XML documents, called diff. However, the question how to correctly apply the changes in a patch is neglected most of the time. We consider this question as important as the diff problem itself. Especially in a distributed collaboration environment, patching is a frequent task; every change, called delta, has to be propagated to all workspaces to ensure a consistent state of all working copies of a file.

Patching a file with the delta it was computed for is an easy task. In contrast, it is not trivial to merge two or more deltas. This is the case when a file is edited simultaneously by two people: Changes between the original and the edited versions have to be merged as far as possible.

In this paper we present a rule set which ensures a high quality of the merge result with respect to the document order of nodes. We will show the benefits of our approach in an experimental setup using office documents.

INTRODUCTION

Documents are the basis of office work. In the past, they evolved in a linear way, as the document was tied to the paper it was written on. The use of computers for document processing, and the spread of networks in offices caused a fundamental break in the view towards documents. They can be edited simultaneously by different people, thus enforcing a new, non-linear evolution of documents. One result of the ubiquitous internet access is the fact a document may be shared with a lot of people, all contributing to it.

A basic need for such collaboration on documents is the capability to propagate edit operations performed on a document. Using an operation-based approach, these edit operations are recorded during the editing itself [Ignat2006]. In some cases - especially in the domain of office work - concerns exist to disclose the edit process. Only an approved document version will be provided for propagation. As we focus our work on the office domain, we constrain this paper on a state-based approach.

In the last decade, XML has emerged as ubiquitous exchange format for data and documents. OpenOffice, Microsoft Office, and many other applications use XML dialects for serializing and exchanging documents. Therefore, in this paper we consider XML documents only. In this context, XML documents are regarded to be ordered by their physical representation in the file. This definition traces the outline in contrast to a data-centric view towards XML, which is commonly used in the domain of databases [Leonardi2005].

In order to find all changes made between two versions of a document, a diff tool is used. It computes a delta, which contains edit operations performed on the document. This delta is used to construct the new version of a document on a different machine using a patch tool. A main problem in this scenario appears, when two persons create different versions of a document independently. As the propagated deltas refer to the same version as source for the construction of the new version, a conflict appears. In this case, the changes have to be merged.

In this paper, we present a context-oriented technique for merging changes in XML documents.

DISTRIBUTED COLLABORATION

In this paper, A refers to a document. A' , A'' , and A^* are versions of A . The delta describing the changes between A , and A' is denoted as $\Delta_{A \rightarrow A'}$, where $\text{diff}(A, A') = \Delta_{A \rightarrow A'}$. An empty delta means that the file has not been changed. The patch constructs the new version using the delta: $\text{patch}(A, \Delta_{A \rightarrow A'}) = A'$.

In the traditional approach, there exist only one time axis and each document has a linear evolution basically. Centralized version control systems support this approach.

The designated workflow for documents in such a system is to check out a document, which means that you transmit the corresponding file to your local machine, update it locally, and check it in again, using a delta to avoid a complete retransmission of the document.

A major problem in this approach is the concurrent editing of documents, as shown in Figure 1. Two persons check out the same version and try to check in consecutively. Alice transmits her delta, describing the changes she made between the document versions A , and A' . Unfortunately, Bob did his check-in earlier, so that the valid version of document A is A'' . As the version control system does not want to reject the changes of Alice on principle, a merge of the changes made by Alice and Bob has to be performed. This would typically be done using a three-way diff tool, comparing the changes performed with the nearest common ancestor of the document version [Lindholm2006, Khanna2007].

In distributed collaboration, however, a main property is the lack of a linear time-model. Furthermore, no defined workflow exists. Each person tracks her local changes and will be notified for updated versions by other persons occasionally. The deltas would be spread by e-mail or downloaded via internet typically.

Note that the term *distributed* does not refer to a meaning like used in the domain of grid computing. A substantial property of distributed collaboration is that not every change is propagated and that not everyone holds an actual copy of any document.

Figure 1: In centralized repositories, concurrent edits could lead to conflicts

Figure 2: In distributed collaboration, changes are only propagated if triggered, thus allowing each workspace to have a different state.

Figure 2 shows an example scenario. Since no superordinate authority exists, it is almost impossible to decide, which version acts as the nearest common ancestor of two versions of a document. Therefore, we try to apply a delta to a version of a document it was not computed for. This is an erroneous operation, as most deltas define the position of an edit operation by use of a fixed address within the document. However, most changes performed on a document affect the addresses of the subsequent document, which leads to unwanted results easily.

INTELLIGENT MERGING OF XML DOCUMENTS

We distinct following edit operations on document trees: *insert*, *delete*, and *update*, which have following properties:

- ❖ An *insert* operation addresses the position in the document tree, where a new subtree will be inserted. Any already existent node/subtree at this position will be shifted to the right, including the subsequent tree rooted at the same parent node, as shown in Figure 3.
- ❖ A *delete* operation addresses the node to delete. Any subtree rooted at this node will be deleted as well.
- ❖ An *update* operation acts uniquely on the node addressed.

Note that insert and delete operations address whole subtrees. The main intention for this decision was to avoid ambiguous edit operations, in particular with respect to possible merges. This behaviour conforms with [Marian2001, Chawathe1997], but is contradictory to [Lindholm2004, Lindholm2006].

A key question dealing with XML diff is how to define the address of an edit operation. XPath provides a powerful language to address nodes within XML documents. However, XPath expressions usually return a set of nodes, whereas an edit operation must act on a unique node. To avoid this, XPath allows the addressing of single nodes on a hierarchy level using an absolute index. To guarantee a unique address, an absolute index must be used on each hierarchy level. In our approach, we use a simple and slightly updated subset of XPath presented in [Lindholm2006].

As already stated before, we regard the order of the document as essential. In addition, we assume this (syntactic) document order to be associated with the semantic order of the document defined by the persons editing the document. To exemplify, just consider a text document. The semantic order of sections and paragraphs are not defined in terms of machine-readable rules - it still conforms with the (syntactic) document order strictly.

We assume every edit operation to stand within a context in that

document order. The context of an edit operation consists of the nodes being in document order within a given radius r around that edit operation. We must be precise that a subtree to delete is not part of this context, as it would refer to itself otherwise.

Figure 3: Each insert and delete operation requires to re-label all following nodes to ensure a correct addressing scheme.

In general, the context of an edit operation has a higher priority during merge as its address. However, the address is used as starting

point for the search for the correct match. Thus, we constrain this search for complexity reasons to a neighborhood, as stated in [Rönnau2005]. In the present implementation, the neighborhood exclusively consists of nodes on the same hierarchy level as the addressed node. However, there exist special cases where this constraint is too strict. In OpenOffice for example, a paragraph moved between from a section to a subsection will also lead to an according change of the hierarchy level in the XML representation. Further research will be spent in finding more suitable rules for neighbourhood generation.

Re-labeling of an XML tree becomes necessary for all nodes standing right of any insert or delete operations to ensure that they can be addressed in a correct way, as shown in Figure 3. On the one hand, this is a very cost-intensive operation [Ko2006]. On the other hand, this re-labeling can disturb subsequent edit operations, as they rely on addresses with respect to the original document.

To avoid this hazard, we use a merge run consisting of two phases. In the first phase, all edit operations are checked and their correct position for application is found. These positions are stored using pointers to the in-memory representation of the document tree. In the second phase, the edit operations are applied sequentially acting on these pointers which will not be affected by previous insert and delete operations.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We tested our approach using example OpenOffice documents. We extracted edit operations which were recorded using the “track changes” feature using a simple program we wrote for that purpose. After extracting the edit operations,

	Trad. approach with conflict detection	Trad. approach without conflict detection	Context-oriented approach
Positives	69%	100%	93%
False positives	0%	31%	7%
Negatives	31%	0%	0%

Table 1: The context-oriented approach combines both the flexibility of finding moved edit operations and a high reliability of the result.

we undid the changes in the documents and performed different edits which were extracted and so on.

This way, we incrementally extracted 84 edit operations out of 5 documents. The patch procedure had the task to apply these edit operations on the document version it was computed for as well as on different versions created, resulting in over 900 test-runs. As a result, 31% of the edit operations had to be merged. The correct application of edit operations was verified by using the “compare documents” feature of OpenOffice.

We compared our context-oriented approach with the traditional approach, which only relies on the address of an edit operation. Concerning the traditional approach, we distinguished between implementations with and without conflict detection. The former approach would refuse to apply an edit operation to a node which had been updated in the meantime, whereas the latter one would apply each edit operation, disregarding its present content. Table 1 shows the results.

Obviously, the traditional approach lacks the ability to deal with edit operations addressing wrong positions. The test results indicate that our approach provides a high reliability of merge operations, which were done right at a rate of 77%. This reliability could be improved using an additional conflict detection, which has already been implemented. However, our test scenario showed that OpenOffice has the property to be robust against small changes in the XML representation of the documents, for example white space handling. Thus, we disabled our conflict detection in order to achieve more positives and to take the risk of more false positives.

RELATED WORK

In the line-based domain, context orientation is established [FSF2002], an according application to the XML domain is not known to us.

To avoid the addressing problem, some approaches in-line the version information into the document itself [Fontaine2002, Rosado2007]. However, this approach needs to transmit the complete document over network for every transaction, which makes it unusable for distributed collaboration. Another

approach is to tag every node with a persistent identifier [Marian2001, Cobéna2002]. This approach is only usable in the context of the framework managing those identifiers; the drawback in the domain of distributed collaboration is obvious.

Approaches exist to define edit operations on XML documents in a general way [Bruno2003, Tatarinov2001, Lam2002]. However, these approaches use a database centric view towards XML documents and are not able to deal with documents updated in the meantime either, as they also use XPath expressions or similar languages for addressing nodes.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we show the importance of merging in the domain of distributed collaboration using XML documents. To avoid the cost-intensive transmission of whole documents, we focus on the merge of deltas, which just describe the changes between two document versions.

To find the correct position of an edit operation, we use its context within the document as more reliable information than its absolute path. We define a neighborhood around an edit operation, where the possibly moved edit operation is searched. Thus, we ensure an efficient merge, as an exhaustive search is avoided.

Experimental results indicate that our approach is able to merge changes well. The advantage compared to the traditional approach based on absolute paths is impressive.

However, we feel confident that the merge results can still be better. Future work will focus on the question how to improve the neighborhood generation for finding the appropriate position of an edit operation.

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